

DIDACTIC SYSTEM FOR DEVELOPING PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS IN STUDENTS

H.O.Akhmedova

The Academy of Armed Forces the Republic of Uzbekistan
Head of the department of "LANGUAGES" associate professor
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10349120>

Annotation. In this article, the successful solution of complex issues, such as educating the younger generation in the future as a harmonious person, independent thinker, depends in many ways on the ideological beliefs, professional skills, knowledge, culture of the teacher. A modern educator needs to know how to influence the student, shaping his or her desires, beliefs, interests, and abilities. This means that a modern school needs a highly educated, active researcher, teacher-educator.

Keywords: Skill, educator, student, education, upbringing, need, ability, worldview, problem, skill, young generation, alphabet, will, quality, influence, teacher.

Introduction. The question arises as to what kind of pedagogical-psychological training, pedagogical knowledge, professional skills, pedagogical abilities and qualities a teacher, in particular, an elementary school teacher should have? We will try to answer these questions through the article. Based on the modern achievements of pedagogical science, it is very important to create ways of formation of pedagogical skills in future primary school teachers and some of its theoretical foundations in accordance with the requirements of the time. Given the diversity and complexity of the tasks of shaping and developing a harmoniously developed generation, the problem of pedagogical skills is the most pressing issue, given the urgent need for educational theory and practice. A skilled educator is essential for all educational institutions.

In this regard, pedagogical skills are a system of professional skills and competencies for the optimization of education, mainly to guide the younger generation, to develop and improve their spiritual beliefs, worldview, abilities in terms of social needs. The multifaceted and complexity of the problem of forming a new person shows the importance of the problem of pedagogical skills for modern educational theory and practice. Because the skills of the educator, his maturity, deep professional knowledge, skills and abilities to determine the perfect upbringing of a person in all respects, to determine his future, cannot be achieved without special knowledge and experience.

In particular, a teacher's needs and beliefs cannot be shaped by his or her abilities and practical skills without a skilled educator. The primary school teacher is the head and alphas of the learners. That is why they need to be masters of their profession. At the same time, it is no exaggeration to say that it is one of the most pressing issues of our time. To be a good teacher, a teacher must work tirelessly on himself. L. Talstoy wrote a classic description of a real teacher: If a teacher is only interested in his work, he will be a good teacher. If a teacher is just as envious as his father, his mother, he will be better than the previous teacher. If he integrates, then he will be a perfect teacher. Being a good teacher depends not only on the teaching system, but also on the behavior of the learner. However, a didactic system focused on developing pedagogical skills in students can be beneficial. Such a system can provide structured guidance, resources, and strategies to help students enhance their teaching abilities. By incorporating various instructional techniques, feedback mechanisms, and practical experiences, students can improve their capacity to effectively engage and educate others. Additionally, the use of technology and interactive platforms within this system could further enhance the learning experience for aspiring educators.

Didactic is the science or discipline of teaching and instruction. It encompasses the theories, methods, and principles of education, focusing on how to effectively deliver knowledge and facilitate learning. Didactic aims to enhance the teaching-learning process by providing educators with strategies and techniques to engage and motivate learners, organize instructional materials, and assess learning outcomes. It involves understanding learners' needs and abilities, designing appropriate learning environments, and utilizing various instructional tools and technologies. Didactic also emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development for educators to improve their teaching practices and adapt to evolving educational contexts. To improve didactic practices, here are a few suggestions:

1. Use active learning strategies: Encourage participation and engagement by incorporating activities that require students to actively manipulate or apply knowledge. This can include group discussions, problem-solving exercises, simulations, role-plays, and hands-on experiments.

2. Tailor instruction to individual needs: Recognize that students have diverse learning styles, interests, and abilities. Differentiate instruction by presenting

information in various formats, providing alternative assignments or pathways to learning, and offering extra support or enrichment based on students' needs.

3. Utilize technology effectively: Leverage the power of technology to enhance the learning experience. Include multimedia elements such as videos, interactive simulations, and online resources to supplement the traditional classroom instruction. Use virtual platforms for collaborative projects, real-time feedback, and assessment.

4. Foster a supportive and inclusive learning environment: Create a classroom atmosphere that encourages collaboration, respect, and diversity. Emphasize the value of different perspectives and ideas, and provide opportunities for students to express their thoughts and opinions without fear of judgment.

5. Provide timely and constructive feedback: Regularly assess student progress and provide feedback that is specific, actionable, and focuses on both strengths and areas for improvement. Encourage self-reflection and goal-setting to help students take ownership of their learning.

6. Continuously update and reflect on your teaching practices: Stay updated with the latest research, trends, and innovations in education. Attend professional development workshops, conferences, and webinars. Reflect on your teaching methods, seek feedback from students and colleagues, and make necessary adjustments to improve your instructional approach.

Remember, effective didactic practices are a constant work in progress, and it is important to listen and be responsive to the needs of your students while being open to new ideas and approaches.

Didactic is the science or discipline of teaching and instruction. It encompasses the theories, methods, and principles of education, focusing on how to effectively deliver knowledge and facilitate learning. Didactic aims to enhance the teaching-learning process by providing educators with strategies and techniques to engage and motivate learners, organize instructional materials, and assess learning outcomes. It involves understanding learners' needs and abilities, designing appropriate learning environments, and utilizing various instructional tools and technologies. Didactic also emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development for educators to improve their teaching practices and adapt to evolving educational contexts. Therefore, the teaching system in higher

education helps to build and understand the learning process for the future teacher. First of all, it is necessary to focus on ensuring the achievement of high professional skills in the process of teaching the requirements of higher education. The development of pedagogical skills in students is the coordinating basis for the training of future teachers. The solution of this problem requires a teacher to be extremely diligent, creative, able to evaluate their work, as well as to treat children in a humane manner. The pedagogical skills of a teacher, if we look at history, we see that the education of the perfect man has always been in the minds of our ancestors, in the center of attention. It is not in vain that our president added to Amir Temur's phrase "Power is in justice" "Power is in knowledge and thinking". Because the more democratic, enlightened and intelligent young people there are in the society, the more progress will inevitably develop in the society. After all, our educated young men and women contribute to the development of our society. At the same time, of course, the skills of educators are great. Only when the teacher is in a certain position towards the students can he / she successfully exert pedagogical influence. This situation is the main guide of the student in the field of interaction with students, which is consistent with the psychological age characteristics of students. The way and skill of the teacher, who is the subject of influencing the behavior of students of different ages, is very important. Interaction with the student body is often in the form of conversations, lectures, information. First of all,

we will talk about how to start a conversation, how to immediately draw children's

attention to the student's words, their interest. In this case, the teacher has the task to explain very briefly, but clearly enough, during the interview. Any conversation should be able to engage children. Therefore, a true educator must have not only knowledge but also norms of speaking. In the school process, the two main

participants are the teacher and the student. The fact that these two people have a proper relationship with each other during the lesson has an operative educational effect on the formation of the student's personality. As mentioned above, the teacher should address the student, taking into account the psychological characteristics and abilities of the student. In the course of the lesson, the educator should try not to demean the teacher, but only through command, jerking. The teacher must be able to understand the rights of the student independently. The educator must not only impart knowledge, but also

nurture the citizen as a person who feels responsible for the lives of others and himself. This is achieved through struggle, pedagogical skills, abilities and relationships. The need for the teacher to work independently, to improve their professional skills will be related to the growth of society's demand and attention to the school, the teacher, his personality, or to new social needs for education.

Organization of teacher's work in the scientific field. Creativity, ingenuity, creativity is a complex mental process, which is, first of all, closely connected with the thinking, worldview, independent activity, memory, attention, will of teachers. Scientific organization of teacher's work means the creation of innovations in the creative organization of their work, using the latest achievements of pedagogy, psychology to manage the pedagogical process. Independent work on the teacher increases skills and creativity. In order for a teacher to educate himself, he must first study himself in depth, be able to see his own strengths and weaknesses. It is necessary to study oneself and understand the other person as well. The task of the educator is not only to show the scope of volitional qualities, to reveal their internal connection with important ethical principles, but also to help the student who seeks to cultivate his own will, to use a wide range of methods of developing volitional qualities. In order for a student to educate himself, he must first study himself in depth, be able to see the successes and shortcomings of his work. It is also important to understand himself and other people. It is impossible to study oneself as a person without learning other achievements and comparing oneself with others. Self-awareness, a feature of self esteem, is formed in the process of interaction with other people, during joint activities.

Conclusion. The modern educator must be able to teach the younger generation, to educate, to influence the student, to shape his desires, beliefs, interests and abilities. The task of the educator is not only to show the scope of volitional qualities, to reveal their inner connection with important moral principles, but also to help the student who seeks to educate his own will, to develop volitional qualities as children who benefit the Motherland.

References:

1. S.T.Kalandarova// Teaching methods and ways of developing communicative competences of students// Scientific and technical journal Sustainable Agriculture ISSN 2181-9408.3(7).2020
2. S.T.Kalandarova// Suggestion Interdisciplinary approach forming business communication skills in the English language (on the example of

information technology science)// Berlin Studies Transnational journal of Science and Humanities ISSN 2748-0866 Vol.2 Issue 1/5 Pedagogical sciences <http://berlinstudies.de/> 10.528/6091942

3. N.N Azizkhodjaeva// Use of pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. Samarkand-2009. B. 52-57.

4. Sh.Urakov, Sh.Eshpulatov The use of pedagogical technologies in the training of

5. future teachers. Samarkand-2009. B. 52-57.